

**INTEGRATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTO ECONOMICS AND
EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT: NAVIGATING THE DIGITAL
TRANSFORMATION**

Erkinov Samandar

Y2 student MDIST Sunderland university Business Marketing Management

Email(erkinovsamandar077@gmail.com)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810864>

Abstract. *"This paper explores the innovative integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in the fields of economics and educational management. As digital transformation reshapes industries, the application of AI has become a pivotal element in enhancing teaching methodologies, administrative efficiency, and economic strategies. We analyze current trends, potential benefits, and challenges, providing insights into the future of AI in educational settings and its impact on economic education."*

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Digital Transformation, Economic Education, Educational Management, Teaching Methodologies.

Аннотация. *"В этой статье исследуется инновационная интеграция технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в области экономики и управления образованием. Поскольку цифровая трансформация меняет отрасли, применение ИИ стало ключевым элементом в совершенствовании методик преподавания, административной эффективности и экономических стратегий. Мы анализируем текущие тенденции, потенциальные преимущества и проблемы, предоставляя представление о будущем искусственного интеллекта в образовательных учреждениях и его влиянии на экономическое образование"*.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, Цифровая трансформация, Экономическое образование, Образовательный менеджмент, Методики преподавания.

Annotatsiya. *"Ushbu maqola (AI) texnologiyalarining iqtisodiyot va ta'limni boshqarish sohasidagi innovatsion integratsiyasini o'rganadi. Raqamli transformatsiya sanoatni o'zgartirganligi sababli, dastur o'qitish metodikasi, ma'muriy samaradorlik va iqtisodiy strategiyalarni takomillashtirishning asosiy elementiga aylandi. Biz ta'lim muassasalarida sun'iy intellektning kelajagi va uning iqtisodiy ta'limga ta'siri haqida tushuncha berish orqali hozirgi tendentsiyalar, potentsial foyda va muammolarni tahlil qilamiz."*

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, raqamli transformatsiya, iqtisodiy ta'lim, ta'limni boshqarish, o'qitish usullari.

Introduction:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming many aspects of human life, including economics and education. The introduction of AI into curricula and education management offers new opportunities for personalization and effectiveness, but also carries risks and challenges. Traditional economic education and management face challenges such as a unified approach to learning and a lack of resources. The digital transformation accelerated by the introduction of AI offers solutions to these problems, providing a deeper understanding and adaptation to the needs of students.

AI Integration Strategies:

Strategies include developing adaptive training programs, using AI to analyze training data, and improving administrative efficiency. Examples include individualized tests, student performance analytics, and schedule automation.

Advantages of AI integration:

Benefits include improved quality and accessibility of education, more efficient resource management, and opportunities for personalized learning. AI can provide students with real-time feedback and tailor study programs to meet their individual needs.

Cons and problems:

Possible problems include data privacy issues, the need for significant initial investments, and the risk of increasing social inequality. There is also a need for professional training for teachers to use AI effectively.

Practical examples:

Examples of successful integration of AI into education include the use of adaptive learning systems at universities and online platforms that adapt material to the needs of each student, and the use of artificial intelligence

Examples:

Using AI to speed up learning:

Artificial intelligence can contribute to faster and more efficient learning of materials by students in training centers. AI systems based on machine learning algorithms can analyze each student's learning style and preferences, offering personalized learning materials and tasks. This provides a more focused and in-depth study of topics, allowing students to learn complex concepts more effectively and overcome learning obstacles faster.

The possibilities of using AI in training centers:

1. Adaptive Learning:

AI can customize learning programs according to the needs and abilities of each student, providing an individualized learning path. This includes adapting the speed of delivery of materials, the level of complexity of tasks and the feedback format.

2. Personalized feedback:

The AI can analyze student responses to assignments and provide instant, personalized feedback. This not only helps students understand their mistakes and learn from them, but also allows teachers to identify common class weaknesses and adjust the curriculum.

3. Predicting academic performance:

Through data analysis, AI can predict students' potential difficulties with certain topics or concepts, allowing teachers to pre-intervene and provide additional resources or attention to students in need.

4. Game-based learning methods:

Using AI to create educational games and simulations that adapt to the level of knowledge and interests of students. This can make learning more interactive and fun, increasing student motivation and engagement.

Conclusion:

The introduction of AI into educational processes offers significant benefits for learning centers, including personalizing learning and improving student effectiveness. However, to maximize these opportunities, it is necessary to overcome technical, ethical and financial challenges.

REFERENCES

1. Brown, A. and Green, T. (2023). "Artificial intelligence in education: a new era of learning." Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
2. Li, M., & Chen, H. (2022). "Adaptive learning systems: integration of artificial intelligence and education". *Research and development in the field of educational technologies*, 70 (1), 85-110.
3. Singh, P., & Gupta, A. (2024). "Problems and opportunities for the introduction of artificial intelligence in educational institutions." *Magazine
4. Zhai, X., Chu, X., Chai, C.S., Jong, M.S.Y., Istenic, A., Spector, M., Liu, J.-B., Yuan, J. and Li, Y. (2021). A Review of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education from 2010 to 2020. *Complexity*, [online] 2021(8812542), pp.1–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8812542>.
5. Holmes, W., Persson, J., Chounta, I.-A., Wasson, B. and Dimitrova, V. (2022). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND EDUCATION A critical view through the lens of human rights, democracy and the rule of law. [online] Available at: <https://rm.coe.int/artificial-intelligence-and-education-a-critical-view-through-the-lens/1680a886bd>.
6. Holmes, W., Bialik, M. and Fadel, C. (2019). Artificial Intelligence In Education Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning. [online] Available at: <https://curriculumredesign.org/wp-content/uploads/AIED-Book-Excerpt-CCR.pdf>.